

**«ШКОЛА ДЛЯ ДУРАКОВ» САШИ СОКОЛОВА:
К ВОПРОСУ ОБ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ПОЭТИЧЕСКОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ РОМАНА /
SASHA SOKOLOV'S "SCHOOL FOR FOOLS": ON THE QUESTION
OF STUDYING THE POETIC STRUCTURE OF THE NOVEL**

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Intertextuality, fragmentariness, eclecticism, a combination of various styles and genres, a mixture of illusion and history, myth and modernity, a blending of different languages, cultures, truths emphasize the modernist and post-modern orientation of the novel “The School for Fools” by Sasha Sokolov. The theme of creativity and madness permeates the entire novel: the title, the image of the protagonist, the schizophrenic discourse, the associative narrative structure, and the author's position are all subordinate to the motif of creative creation.